

Table 1. Estimates of variations in physiological parameters,^a Jabalpur, India, 1978-79.

	LAI	LAR	LWR	SLA	RGR	CGR	NAR	Seed yield (t/ha)
Mean	3.38	63.17	.268	229.1	.046	31.63	10.58	4.75
Minimum	1.81	16.91	.15	105.6	.016	13.67	7.63	3.08
Maximum	4.38	82.35	.35	330.9	.083	50.27	12.36	5.74
Phenotypic variance	1.03	359.52	.004	3766.4	.00054	107.06	2.54	7.99
Genotypic variance	0.77	269.65	.003	858.0	.00048	63.00	0.54	6.53
Environmental variance	0.26	89.87	.001	2908.4	.00056	44.06	3.08	1.46
pcv	30.05	30.02	24.88	26.79	50.43	32.69	15.02	18.81
gcv	25.96	25.99	21.66	23.54	1.05	25.09	6.92	16.99
h ² B (%)	74.6	75.0	75.7	22.7	89.6	58.0	21.1	81.6
G.A.	8.22	29.29	0.104	28.70	0.043	12.36	0.69	15.03
G.A. as % of mean	243.28	46.37	38.81	12.53	93.24	39.07	6.54	31.62

^a LAI = leaf area index, LAR = leaf area ratio, LWR = leaf weight ratio, SLA = specific leaf area, RGR = relative growth rate, CGR = crop growth rate, NAR = net assimilation rate, pcv = coefficient of variation for phenotype, gcv = coefficient of variation for genotype.

tion (LAD), LWR, seed yield, and SLA; of LAR with LAD, SLA, and seed yield; of LAD with LWR, seed yield, and RGR; and of SLA with seed yield. RGR correlated positively and significantly with CGR, but negatively and nonsignificantly with seed yield (Table 2).

This study indicates LAI and RGR are the only characters that significantly influence economic productivity of rice cultivars. *✎*

Table 2. Multiple correlation of physiological parameters,^a Jabalpur, India, 1978-79.

Parameter	LAR 2	LAD 3	LWR 4	SLA 5	RGR 6	CGR 7	Yield 8
1 LAI	.881**	.892**	.855**	.329*	.080	-.116	.453**
2 LAR		.798**	.755**	.623**	.0838	.166	.558**
3 LAD			.794**	.258	.313*	-.140	.388*
4 LWR				.013	.144	.105	.453**
5 SLA					-.085	.155	.418**
6 RGR						.491**	.411*
7 CGR							.082

^a LAI = leaf area index, LAR = leaf area ratio, LAD = leaf area duration, LWR = leaf weight ratio, SLA = specific leaf area, RGR = relative growth rate, CGR = crop growth rate.

Emergence of calcium peroxide-coated rice seed at different water depths

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The effect of submergence depth on germination of calcium peroxide-coated seed was studied in pot culture. Plastic containers 24 cm deep and 20 cm in diameter were filled with 6 kg soil, ground to pass through 2-mm pores. Pusa 37 seeds, uncoated and coated with 40% and 64% by weight of calcium peroxide, were seeded uniformly at 100 seeds/pot. Soil was maintained either 1) in saturated condition, 2) with 1 cm standing water, 3) with 2 cm standing water, or 4) with 3 cm standing water. Each treatment had three replications.

In saturated soil, calcium peroxide coating adversely affected seed germination (see figure). Of seeds with 64% cal-

cium peroxide coating, only 12% germinated. Germination of uncoated seeds was 72%.

In standing water, germination and seedling emergence of calcium peroxide-coated seeds increased. In 1 cm standing water, more seeds germinated with 64% coating than with 40% coating. In 2 cm

standing water, the 2 coating levels were equally effective. In 3 cm standing water, fewer seeds germinated with 64% coating. As depth of standing water increased, germination and seedling emergence of uncoated rice seeds decreased. All germinated seeds emerged. *✎*

Germination (%)

Effect of calcium peroxide coating on germination and seedling emergence in rice. IARI, New Delhi, India.